

THE RESEARCH OF PILGRIMAGE ADDRESSES IN SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation: Today, in a period of extensive development of tourism, it is thought that pilgrimage tourism has its place among other types of tourism. A plan has been drawn up to turn these places, which are located in Samarkand region, but unknown to the population, into tourism destinations. In this article, we will focus on the architecture of neglected pilgrimage sites around the city of Samarkand and their current status.

Key words: Shrine, pilgrimage, Imam Ali Sugdi, Kumushkent, Miyanqul, Hanafiya madhhab, Shovdar, Kocha Malik, Sugd Khurd, Sugdi Kalon, Kabud, Navbog, Yoryailaq, Anhor Jadid, Shiroz Aliabad Sogarj, Shodmon and Ishtikhan, Said Nurmuhhammad Khoja, Arab-Ota, Samanid, Ashiq-Ota.

Samarkand has always been a land of religious scholars. There are many visiting places in today's Samarkand city and around of it. There are many places of pilgrimage in the city center, which are popular and the center of attention among the locals. But the suburbs of Samarkand are known only among the people who live in the pilgrimage destination, and others do not know them. In this article, we will focus on the architecture of neglected pilgrimage sites around the city of Samarkand and their current status.

Architecture of Imam Ali Sugdi complex. Islam Imam Ali Sugdi, honored with the name "Pillar of Islam", one of the greatest scholars of fiqh; He was born at the beginning of the 11th century in Sogd of Samarkand (now Kumushkent region of Okhdarya), died in 1069 and was buried in Kumushkent region of Okhdarya. One of the greatest scholars of science and fiqh. In his time, he was the head of the Hanafiya madhhab of the whole Islamic world.

Figure 1. Imam Ali Sugdi complex

Despite the fact that the cemetery on the outskirts of Kumushkent district of Akdarya district is ancient and has become a ruin, its beauty is noticeable. In the middle of the cemetery there is a large mound like a hut, on which four dilapidated graves stand side by side. According to the elders, there was once a mosque-khanaqah near this hut-hill.

In the Middle Ages, the land between the Aqdarya and Karadarya rivers in the region was called Miyanqul, and even more anciently, Sug'd. Since the time of the Timurids, the land of Samarkand was mainly divided into fourteen districts. At different times, there were different numbers of districts in Samarkand. They are the following: Shovdar, Anhor, Kocha Malik, Sugd Khurd, Sugdi Kalon, Kabud, Navbog, Yoryailaq, Anhor Jadid, Shiroz Aliabad Sogarj, Shodmon and Ishtikhan districts. Two of these districts were called "Sug'di Kalon" (Big Sug'd) and "Sug'd Khurd" (Little Khurd). Kumushkent district, which we are interested in, is located in Sugdi district, which is sometimes called "Nimsugd" (Half Sugd). In the 16th century, during the Shaibani dynasty, the name of the district was changed and it was called "Ofarinkent" district. The district occupied the upper northern part of Mionkol Island between Okdarya and Karadarya, and according to some sources, it occupied the north-western part of the city of Samarkand, the southeastern part of Mionkol Island. Since ancient times, the land between two rivers has been called "Samakarkand Sugdi". Khartang, Sogarch, Ishtikhan, Ofarinkent, Dahbed, etc., were considered the most ancient and famous areas of Samarkand Sughd. According to the historical waqfnama and wasikanomas, these lands were included in the Khurd district of Sughd. The district is bordered by Sogarj district from the north. The center of Sugdi Khurd district is Ofarinkent (Prinkent) region, which was founded by the Sugd king Gurak at the beginning of the 8th century (the Gurak-Arab caliphate was a local king during the conquest of Central Asia).

In accordance with the "clause" of the Cabinet of Ministers' Decision on International Conferences dedicated to the memory of our Great Imams - Imam Moturidi and Imam Marginani, the spiritual disciple of Imam al-Moturidi, Imam Marg' It is both a debt and a duty for us to improve the graves of Hazrat Imam Ali

Sugdi, one of the direct teachers of Inani. We hope that those in charge of implementing the decision will carry out this meritorious work. On the eve of finishing the book, in collaboration with several major scientists, an appeal was made to the governor of Samarkand region about the restoration of the mausoleum of the great Imam Ali Sugdi in Kumushkent district of Okdarya district, and as a result of this appeal, a meeting was held under the leadership of the governor of Okdarya district, and beautification activities were carried out.

The architecture of the shrine of Said Nurmuhhammad Khoja. (Figure 2) In accordance with the decision of the governor of the Okdarya district of Samarkand region No. 300-k dated December 2, 1999, research works were carried out in the cemetery in the village of Pichachchi, Okdarya district. Information about the life and work of Sheikh Syed Nurmuhhammad Khoja was obtained from Eshon Akramov Aslan Khoja, his 10th generation ancestor, who lived in this village and restored the grave of his famous grandfather. The studied object is located in the territory of the cemetery of the village of Pichachchi, Okdarya district, and has become a place where grass has grown. The grave belongs to the famous Sheikh Syed Nurmuhhammad

Figure 2. Shrine of Said Nurmuhhammad Khoja

Khoja. Sheikh Sayit Nurmuhhammad Khoja was born in Khorezm at the beginning of the 18th century. He received his education in Bukhara. He was a representative of the famous Naqshbandi sect. He practiced healing and prophecy (sainthood) and was the spiritual teacher of Amir Abdulaziz Khan and

Muhammadaziz Khan for a long time. After the enmity caused by the injustices, he asked the ruler of Samarkand for a land like a "tip of a knife", from which the village of "Pichok Uchi" was called "Pichok Uchi", which was later transformed into a more simplified village. This village is now called Pichakhchi. In 1730, 444 acres of land was allocated to him 30 km away from Samarkand, in the territory of a modern village, and he was buried there. During his lifetime, the Sheikh was famous as a famous healer, especially in the field of infertility treatment. The sheikh's lineage goes back from the Sayyids to the Prophet Muhammad. Amir Temur's spiritual teacher Mir Syed Baraka was also from the same family. Around Dahbet, in addition to the families belonging to the family of Dahbedi Makhdumi Azam, Sayyid Atoi, i.e. descendants belonging to the family of Sayyid Ota, also worked as representatives of various sects. This breed is famous for being governor. They were engaged in the education of the perfect piri murids of the people of the Tariqat and started the masses on the right path. According to preliminary conclusions, this breed died in 1330 AD. Originally from Khorezm, he was the ancestor of rulers like Abdulaziz Khan and Muhammad Aziz. In 2008, the hut was opened, historical and comparative accuracy was introduced and recorded evidence was enriched. The descendants of Sayyid Nurmuhhammad's disciples and caliphs, as well as relatives, lived in Okdarya, Payariq, Nurota districts. Hazrat Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf's books on Sufism also contain information about a great Sheikh named Sayyid Nur Muhammad Badauni (qs). Information about the place and year of birth is not given, the date of death is 1135 AH and 1722 AD. It is noted that this person has a light sign on his forehead, and that he is a leader in the sciences of Sharia and Tariqat, and that he is also a master of the sciences of Sarf, Nahw, Hadith, and Tafsir. Those who earned an example by their piety: they found the necessary bread flour for their needs from the halal they trusted, made the dough themselves, and baked the bread themselves. They chewed the bread and ate it only when there was an extreme need for consumption. Being an avid reader, they started reading any book they could get their hands on after three days. They are aware of the height of the level of knowledge. They quickly understand the problems faced by their students and solve their problems. It is said that Sayyid Nurmuhhammad took knowledge and guidance from his teacher Sheikh Saifuddin and gave it to his student Habibullah Mazhar Jo Janan Shamsiddin. More accurate information is that this breed was considered the twenty-seventh perfect pir in the Naqshbandi sect.

The architecture of the Arab-father mausoleum.

(2. Figure) Arab-Ota mausoleum in the village of Tim. A number of scientists believe that this structure was built as a mausoleum in 977-978, while P.Sh.Zokhidov believes that it was later converted into a mausoleum, in fact, it is a preserved part of one of the Samanid castles. The Arab-Ota mausoleum is also made of 23 x 23 x 3.5 cm baked bricks, and its internal dimensions are 5.6 x

5.6 meters. Its difference is that the entrance is one, directed through a luxurious porch. Although there is an opinion among scholars that the use of peshtogh in the architecture of Central Asia was known a little before the period under consideration, among the preserved monuments, the Arab-Ota mausoleum can be considered the first example in this respect. Here the peshtogh forms a whole (spherical) wall. The three-quarter (3/4) part of the square at the entrance is placed on a pillar, reminiscent of the entrance in the Samanid mausoleum. Above the arch at the entrance there are three more arches with falling light, this style gives rise to the direction of decorating the upper part of the gables with arches in later periods. The four kunjak between the wall and the dome are in the form of large muqarnas bowls. The columns are patterned. These elegant pillars give the room a cozy and majestic look. The beauty of the mausoleum is its majestic facade. Bricks are picked in pairs in different order. Stitches include hankor patterns. There are Kufic inscriptions from Peshtok stems. Three niches above the porch are decorated with small patterns. The Tomb of the Arab Father is one of the oldest preserved Muslim tombs in Movaraunnahr. The mausoleum is of great importance in terms of its architectural structure. His Peshtogh was the first mature example of the type of buildings created in that period and influenced the development of the architecture of the XI-XII centuries. The front facade of the Mirsaid Bayerom mausoleum in Karmana (Navoi region), which is considered to have been built at the end of the 10th century or the beginning of the 11th century, depending on the construction method, is also a front facade. Its internal dimensions are 4.47x4.4 meters, and it is built of 21x21x2.5 cm brick. In 2015, the archeological monuments located in the district were registered by the employees of the Samarkand Archaeological Institute and the catalog of Nurabad district was published. In this catalog, the location, exact coordinates, appearance, topographical history, photos and drawings of each monument in the village of Tim and the nearby villages of Astonabobo, Sahoba, Changalli, Kochkorli Ota and other villages are included. given Researchers of the Samarkand Institute of Archeology regularly carry out scientific research in the village of Tim, Nurabad district. In particular, in 2022, as a result of the research carried out together with the scientific staff of the institute and local local historians, public inspectors, new rock paintings were registered from streams such as Kuduqchasoy and Tuyatash near the village of Tim.

In particular, on the stone in Kuduqchasoy there are suvori, wild mountain goats, arhar, various geometric symbols, and ancient Turkic-runic inscriptions. Many of these paintings have been eroded and worn down due to long-term effects of natural phenomena.

Scientific and research work is currently being conducted on the detected records. Also, the location of the Kuduqchasoy metal ore deposit was noted. Around this mine, bronze and early medieval pottery and Turkic-runic writing were discovered. Rock paintings from Changallisoy near the village of Tim were also

recorded, and khumdons belonging to the early Middle Ages were discovered and studied. In particular, the khumdons recorded in Changallisoy were built in a two-tier round shape dating back to the early Middle

Figure 3. The Arab-Ota mausoleum

recorded, and the walls of the hearth were made of granite stones. In 2023, it was proved that the pottery and metal vessels found by local residents from the Korgontepa archaeological site in the center of Tim village belong to the Karakhanid period (XI-XII centuries). Also, this year, together with public inspector Ilhom Botirov, the Duniyotash stone picture, located on the left side of Gulbuloksoy, Kurgancha village, Nurabad district, was researched. It was found that there are images of a man, a mountain goat, an arhar, gazelle, a horse, a camel, a goat, a horseman, a stamp, and the image of the sun. In the course of consistent and comprehensive research conducted in the oasis, in addition to these rock paintings, the ancient cemetery and the ruins of village houses were identified and displayed on the map.

In addition, the mausoleum of the Arab father located in the village of Tim did not escape the attention of the officials of the field regarding the effective organization of work related to the preservation of material cultural heritage in our country in the following years, and the solution of existing problematic issues related to them. Due to the fact that this mausoleum needs restoration, construction and repair work, the Arab father's mausoleum was included in the address list of cultural heritage objects for restoration, construction and repair work in 2023-2024 by the Cultural Heritage Agency and the Cultural Heritage Department of Samarkand region. 500 million from budget and non-budgetary funds for the repair and restoration of the mausoleum. It was decided to allocate soum. At the moment, these funds have been allocated, and the process of financing the work to be carried out and preparing estimate documents is underway. Also, measures are being taken to surround the archaeological monuments in this area with a 3D fence.

Architecture of Ashiq-Ota Mausoleum. One of the Sufism scholars of his time, Mavlano Ashiq, the real name of the father is Mavlano Mir Nematullah Ashiq. Also, in these documents, valuable information can be

obtained from the documents about the endowment of lands belonging to the shrine of Mavlano Mir Nematullah Ashiq Ota. Hazrat Mavlana Mir Ne'matullah Ashiq, who is the real father, his name, profession, where and when he was born, may be a bit confusing, but if you come to visit this place, you will find the light of day, leaving no room for questions, the divine in the human heart. there is a silence. Hazrat Mavlano Ne'matullah Ashiq Ata, in the development of education, in the service of teachers, on the basis of the perfection of students, spread light over the years, and as a result of his belonging in the love of creation, in the eyes and words of the murshid and murids, Mavlano Ashiq Ata received the status of Mavlano Ashiq Ata. The reason why this person is called the Loving Father is because he is considered to be one of the true Lovers of Allah. In addition to the name of the Father, the whole Muslim world is considered the spiritual Father. In particular, it is known from the history that the Prophets of Allah and the servants of the Saints were considered as spiritual fathers to all other people. Hazrat Mawlana Mir Nematullah Ashiq Ata was one of the great saints and had many blessings. In his time, people who suffered from severe pain were cured by the permission of Allah due to the prayers of this person. For several years now, many pilgrims have been coming to the mausoleum erected over the graves of Hazrat Mawlana Mir Nematullah Ashiq Ota, bringing peace of mind and spiritual nourishment. There are also reports that Hazrat Mavlano Mir Ne'matullah Ashiq Ota composed "Devon" during his activity, and that he was the owner of a higher authority than mature poetry. This divan is kept in the ToshDSHI SHKM fund of his work "Devoni Ashiq". Around the mausoleum are the graves of famous scholars of their time - Abu Mu'in Sheikh (birth time unknown, died 1112 AH), Amir Haydar Ibn Amir Muhammad Khurasani (died 958 AH), and There are tombstones of several great scholars, such as Shaykh Abdul Karim (died 1017 AH), who had the status of "Sheikh of the Believers" in the z period. Not only Pastdargom, but also residents of villages adjacent to Okdarya district are buried in the cemetery near the shrine of Ashiq Ota. In the 10th century, this neighborhood belonged to the Okdarya district, and today it is called "Ashiq ota". Next to the entrance gate, there is a well-made in memory of Ashraf Akhroorkulov, and it consists of iron bars. Ornamental trees were planted at the entrance to the shrine and beautification works were carried out. A 200-meter road has been built from the entrance gate to the nursery, and a slab has been laid. During the years of independence, attention was paid to the shrine and repair works were carried out. In the 14th century, during the reign of Mirzo Ulug'bek, a tomb was surrounded and a domed shrine was built as a tribute to the graves of teachers and scholars, and during the period of independence, a 6x3m room for reciting the Qur'an was built.

Figure 4. Ashiq-Ota Mausoleum

There are many places of pilgrimage in the city of Samarkand dedicated to the memory of mature scholars, religious and statesmen of their time, and some of them have not been preserved at all. Their lack of promotion among the local population caused the sedan to disappear over time. In this research, we aim to identify and study such pilgrimage destinations, recover information about them, improve pilgrimage destinations based on them and add them to tourism destinations.

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